

Uncovering Nutritional Deficiencies and the Adequacy of Wrap-Around Care for Patients on GLP-1 RAs: A quality improvement audit

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Abstract

Background: Glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP1-RAs) are effective treatments for obesity and Type-2 diabetes, but concerns remain about malnutrition risks with inadequate support. There is no established framework for nutritional screening, dietary assessment nor supplementation for GLP1-RAs users. This study evaluated dietary intake and the quality of support for patients prescribed GLP1-RAs in a primary care setting.

Methods: A mixed-methods quality improvement audit was conducted at a single NHS GP practice in Northamptonshire, UK. Fourteen adults prescribed GLP1-RAs within the past 12 months completed dietary recalls using the validated myfood24 platform and semi-structured telephone interviews. Dietary intake was compared against UK reference nutrient intakes (%RNI). Interviews were analysed thematically to explore patient experiences of GLP1-RAs use and support received.

Results: Whilst prescribed GLP1-RAs, mean daily caloric intake was ~1,300 kcal, with two participants consuming <800 kcal/day. Fibre intake averaged 44.9% of the RNI, while intakes of iron (64.2%), magnesium (79.0%), potassium (68.9%), and vitamin D (39.7%) were consistently below targets during the period assessed (mean days recorded = 4). In contrast, protein intake frequently exceeded requirements (mean 152% RNI). Ultra-processed foods comprised 33% of dietary intake, (lower than the UK population average). Qualitative analysis revealed major gaps in medical follow-up and dietary guidance: several participants relied on online peer groups, reported uncertainty about basic nutrition and described significant appetite suppression leading to meal skipping. While many reported relief from “food noise” and improved self-compassion, others experienced social withdrawal, financial anxiety, and fear of weight regain.

Conclusion: Patients using GLP1-RAs may fail to meet key nutrient requirements despite exceeding protein targets, with many receiving minimal structured support. More research is needed to assess the size of this problem and the health impacts of potentially failing to meet key nutritional requirements.

What is already known on this topic

- In trial settings, GLP-1 receptor agonists result in weight loss and tighter glycaemic control through multiple mechanisms including appetite suppression resulting in lower caloric intake.
- When studied, people with obesity have significant rates of malnutrition and current UK guidance does not mandate structured nutritional monitoring for GLP1-RA users.

What this study adds

- In this cohort of patients on GLP1-RAs many consumed fewer than the recommended calories and fell short of key micronutrient targets despite meeting protein requirements.
- In this population, many reported inadequate medical and dietary follow-up, leading to reliance on peer groups and self-management.
- Patients described both psychological benefits (reduced “food noise”, improved self-compassion) and challenges (social withdrawal, financial anxiety, fear of weight regain).
- A validated dietary tool (myfood24) was acceptable and feasible for patient-led nutritional monitoring.

How this study might affect research, practice or policy

- Structured nutritional assessment and follow-up may be necessary for GLP1-RA users.
- Primary care pilots are needed using digital tools, such as myfood24, to integrate nutritional screening into routine wrap-around support for those prescribed GLP1-RAs.
- Further research is needed in larger, more diverse populations to evaluate the prevalence of following low calorie diets whilst on GLP1-RAs and quantify the extent of nutritional shortfalls.

1. INTRODUCTION

Trials of GLP1-RAs, Semaglutide (Wegovy) and Tirzepatide (Mounjaro), have demonstrated significant weight loss and improved metabolic health¹. However, concerns persist regarding the adequacy of support provided to patients receiving these medications and specifically whether their appetite-suppressing effects could exacerbate malnutrition, which often co-exists with obesity².

Malnutrition in individuals with obesity is characterised by sarcopenia (muscle-wasting) and deficiencies in micronutrients and/or macronutrients³. This results from overconsumption of low-nutrient dense food despite higher caloric intake⁴. This is consistent with evidence demonstrating that over 50% of those living with obesity have a degree of malnutrition (for example, deficiencies in vitamins A, B1, B9, B12, and D, as well as iron, calcium, and magnesium)⁵. Risks are exacerbated by gut inflammation due to microbiome dysbiosis and commonly prescribed drugs in obesity which promote nutrient malabsorption (e.g., diuretics, proton pump inhibitors, ACE inhibitors, metformin, orlistat etc.)⁶. Further appetite suppression by GLP1-RAs may exacerbate these deficiencies, especially without adequate dietary support or access to nutrient-dense food, forming an underexplored risk with new anti-obesity medicines, particularly in real world or more deprived settings.

For example, individuals with obesity facing food insecurity are more likely to have obesity with malnutrition⁷.

Serious complications of malnutrition have already been reported in individuals using anti-obesity medication including Wernicke’s encephalopathy which can result in Korsakoff’s syndrome (an irreversible dementia syndrome)^{8,9}. Although rare, these severe complications highlight the potential consequences of inadequate nutritional monitoring.

Some research has suggested that people taking GLP1-RAs may have a decreased preference for high-fat and sweet foods¹⁰, yet surprisingly little work has examined the broader dietary patterns resulting from GLP1-RA use, with most clinical trials reporting only caloric intake and weight change². To date, only one published study has investigated detailed dietary intake during GLP1-RA treatment: Johnson et al (2025) analysed three-day dietary records from 69 American GLP1-RA users recruited online who were not following a structured meal plan or nutrition programme¹¹. Using the validated Automated Self-Administered 24-Hour Dietary Assessment Tool, they found frequent shortfalls in fibre, calcium, iron, magnesium, potassium, vitamins A, C, D, E, and K, and choline¹². Low Healthy Eating Index scores, reflecting poor adequacy (e.g. insufficient fruit, vegetables, and whole grains) and suboptimal moderation (e.g. excess refined grains, added sugars, and saturated fat), were observed in this cohort, but there was limited discussion of deeper psychological effects and nuanced changes to dietary habits. Notably, only 51% of participants had received information on managing side effects, and just 20% had been referred to a dietitian alongside the medication¹³.

Wrap-around care can be defined as multidisciplinary or lifestyle medicine support in areas such as nutrition, sleep, psychology, physical activity and medication follow-up, some of which is provided by some private dispensers of GLP1-RAs. NHS prescribing for weight control in patients with diabetes began at the end 2023, but patients rarely report receiving counselling at the point of prescription. Current national guidance for weight management lacks robust requirements for nutritional counselling or systematic monitoring for deficiencies¹⁴. Based on this context, this study audits the nutritional intake whilst on GLP1-RA and quality of wrap-around support provided alongside prescribing of GLP1-RAs for patients in a single NHS GP practice over an average of 4 days (range 1-10). We conducted a validated dietary analysis and a qualitative telephone interview inquiring about their weight-loss experience.

2. METHODOLOGY

This project was undertaken as a quality improvement audit within a medical practise in Northants and did not require NHS Research Ethics Committee approval. It was conducted under the supervision of a GP at the practice and patients gave informed, written consent to participate.

2.1 Design

This study employed a mixed-methods design, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative elements. This approach enabled a comprehensive assessment of participants' dietary quality alongside the care they received.

Qualitative data were gathered via semi-structured telephone interviews allowing participants to articulate their experiences of using GLP1-RAs in their own words. This method was chosen to capture nuanced insights into how the medication influenced their lives and the support they receive.

Quantitative dietary data of participants using the medication were collected using myfood24 (patient app system), an online, validated¹⁵, dietary assessment tool that enables users to log their food intake through a searchable UK food database. The tool estimates total caloric intake, macronutrient breakdown, and micronutrient content, providing insight into nutrient adequacy within the recorded diet. The number of days over which each patient's dietary data

was collected ranged from 1 to 10 days. A myfood24 tutorial video was created for the participant's reference allowing them to record diets independently.

2.2 Participants

Participants were adult patients registered at Brackley Medical Centre who had been prescribed GLP1-RAs within the previous 12 months, either privately (n = 10) or through the NHS (n = 4, 3 have type-2 diabetes—none of whom are on insulin). Eligibility criteria included the ability to consent to a telephone interview and complete the myfood24 dietary recall, either independently or assisted over the telephone (Note: there was no significant difference in measured calorie intake between these two groups). Patients were excluded if they had an eating disorder, significant cognitive impairment affecting recall ability, or comorbidities likely to significantly influence dietary intake (e.g., inflammatory bowel disease, gastroparesis or chronic pancreatitis). Out of 17 patients who initially consented to participate, 3 withdrew, resulting in a final sample of 14 participants. The age range was 27 to 73 years (mean age: 54). The sample consisted of 11 women and 3 men.

2.3 Procedure

Eligible patients were identified through electronic health records using prescription and registration codes relevant to GLP1-RA use. Initially, patients received a text message from their GP to gauge interest and explain the study. Those who expressed interest were emailed detailed study information, including a link to the myfood24 dietary recall platform.

Participants were telephoned and a semi-structured interview was conducted using a predetermined script to acquire medication, diet and lifestyle data (see Appendix.5). Responses were entered into a structured Excel spreadsheet during the interview.

2.4 Data Analysis

Qualitative interview data were analysed using Reflexive Thematic Analysis per Braun and Clarke's six-phase framework¹⁶. This involved familiarisation with the interview notes, generating initial codes/sub-themes (important concepts), which were used to develop and refine themes aligned with the research question integrating examples from participants.

Dietary intake data from myfood24 (list of reported foods and associated nutrients per patient) were loaded into R Studio for quantitative analysis. We grouped the data by patient and date to calculate the average daily intake values for calories, macronutrients and micronutrients (see Appendix.2) over the recorded days (mean days = 4). We also loaded patient-specific nutrient target values based on national dietary guidelines (Government Dietary Recommendations, see Appendix.3) to calculate the percentage reference intakes (%RNI) for each individual nutrient. Raw data from myfood24 include a 'Food subcategory' column which we used to manually generate a list of NOVA group 4 UPF subcategories (see Appendix.4) and label each ingredient as UPF/Non-UPF.

Using the participant postcodes, E-food desert indices (1–10) quantify neighbourhood food access based on proximity and density of grocery stores, transport accessibility, local socio-demographics, and e-commerce infrastructure¹⁷. Lower scores indicate food desert characteristics; higher scores suggest greater food security, enabling us to assess the relationship between food access and nutritional intake.

We also distinguished between the types of support our participants received: basic input (e.g. brief counselling or leaflets at point of prescription) versus structured, multidisciplinary

support such as personalised meal plans, fitness and hydration guidance, side-effect management, and access to dietitians or prescriber consults via digital platforms. Note that only half (5/10) of the participants accessing GLP1-RAs receive this organised support.

Based on interview information, we stratified participants by drug (name, dose), food desert index, support type, engagement in scheduled physical activity, and route of access (NHS vs private). To explore predictors of weight loss in Mounjaro (tirzepatide) users (12 of 14 participants), we fitted simple linear models. Since weight-loss values were right-skewed (many small losses, a few larger), we analysed $\log(1 + \text{weight loss})$ to make the data more symmetric and keep model assumptions reasonable. We used stepwise selection (AIC) to identify the most parsimonious set of predictors.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Qualitative data analysis

Analysis of participant accounts revealed four overarching themes: unmet needs in medical support and guidance, the emotional and psychological journey of weight loss, beyond weight: restoring function and renewing hope, and unintended consequences of the drug. Illustrative quotes and interviewer observations supporting these themes are presented in *Appendix 6*.

Unmet needs in medical support and guidance were consistently reported, with participants describing a lack of structured NHS follow-up to assess patients and address any concerns. Inadequate medication reviews resulted in unmanaged side effects, such as dizziness and hypotension, often requiring patient-led adjustments or reliance on online peer groups for advice. This highlighted a broader gap in professional oversight and safe integration of weight-loss treatments with existing medications.

The emotional and psychological journey of weight loss was characterised by both positive and negative experiences. Many participants described a reduction in “food noise,” enabling greater dietary control, self-compassion, and the ability to enjoy food without guilt. However, this was counterbalanced by social and emotional drawbacks: avoidance of social eating due to nausea or diarrhoea, fears of weight regain upon discontinuing treatment, and anxiety about long-term financial affordability.

The third theme captured the transformative impact of treatment on participants’ quality of life. Reports of reduced pain, improved mobility, and increased capacity for daily activities were accompanied by a sense of psychological relief and renewed hope after years of unsuccessful weight-loss attempts. Participants frequently described the medication as a “turning point” or “game changer.”

Finally, participants discussed several unintended consequences of the drug. These included unexpected reductions in alcohol intake, reduced pleasure from food, and a lack of clear dietary guidance to support safe long-term use. Two participants expressed “shock” and worry at the extent of their reduced caloric intake, which they had not realised until completing the myfood24 diary.

Together, these findings illustrate the dual nature of GLP1-RA treatment: while providing significant physical, psychological, and functional benefits, they are also associated with unmet clinical needs, unintended side effects, and ongoing uncertainty about sustainability and long-term management.

3.2. Quantitative dietary analysis

3.2.1. myfood24 engagement by patients and clinicians

Some participants engaged better with independently recording their diets on myfood24 than others: P1 and P12 provided ten days, and P10 provided seven days of dietary data. However, P6 only provided a one-day record. P8, P10 and P13 provided a two-day record. Two participants (P4 and P2) described finding myfood24 useful, as it highlighted dietary restriction they had not previously been aware of.

Recording a day's diet over telephone took ~10 minutes on average and the myfood24 interface was intuitive to use. Although some participants opted for telephone-driven recall, there were no difficulties reported in using the myfood24 platform with 8/14 participants having completed dietary entries independently, indicating that our tutorial video was effective. Qualitative data took ~20 minutes to obtain.

3.2.2. Low caloric intakes on recorded days

Figure 1. Caloric Intake and Mounjaro Dose

A

Average Daily Calories + % Ultra-Processed Calories per Patient

Bar height = Total kcal; Red = UPF kcal; Label = %UPF

B

B. Calorie Intake by Mounjaro Dose

Each dot represents one patient. Boxplots show median and IQR.

A: Average daily caloric intake and %UPF per patient.

B: Caloric intake by Mounjaro dose. No overall group differences detected.

Dunn's test (5 mg vs. 7.5 mg): $p = 0.094$ (adjusted).

Most participants reported caloric intakes well below standard maintenance requirements (~2000/2500 kcal/day for females/males). Two participants averaged fewer than 800 kcal/day (Fig-1A), indicating patterns of very low energy intake within the sample. We considered the possibility that participants who completed the dietary recall independently may have underreported aspects of their diet, lacking the structured guidance and probing questions we used when assisting the participants. Although this cannot be definitively confirmed, there was no significant difference in daily energy intake between participants who completed the

recall independently and those assisted over a phone call (mean KCAL intake: 1234 vs. 1367; Welch's $t(6.5) = -0.41, p = 0.69$; Wilcoxon $W = 16, p = 0.88$).

Mounjaro (tirzepatide) subgroup and predictors of weight loss

After analysing the log-transformed outcome in Mounjaro users, the selected model retained dose and duration as predictors of weight loss. Each 2.5 mg increase in dose corresponded to ~24% more weight loss (95% CI 3%–49%; $p=0.026$), while duration was not statistically significant ($p=0.19$). There was minimal explanatory value from variables such as route of access (NHS/private), physical activity, fibre intake, caloric intake, food desert index or type of support. Caloric intake varied by dose group, with the lowest mean intake observed at 5 mg and the highest at 15 mg. However, no consistent dose-response pattern was evident (Fig-1B).

3.2.3. Nutrient targets were largely unmet

Figure 2. Nutrient Analysis

Calcium, iron, magnesium, potassium, vitamins A, C, D, E, and K, thiamine, folate, cobalamin, and choline deficiencies have been reported in individuals with obesity taking GLP1-RAs or undergoing bariatric surgery^{5,11}. Across the recorded days, most patients had suboptimal intakes for many of these micronutrients (Table-2). Using 100% of the RNI as a threshold for adequacy, none of the 14 participants met requirements for all nutrients assessed. All participants fell below the RNI for at least two nutrients, and five participants had <50% intake for multiple nutrients, suggesting marked risk of insufficiency. Iron, magnesium, potassium and vitamin D targets were significantly below 100%RNI (Fig-2B). Although vitamin D represents the most marked deficiency, its interpretation is complicated by endogenous synthesis via sun exposure and therefore may be less informative in this dietary dataset.

Among macronutrients, fibre intake was notably suboptimal: patients consumed on average only 44.9% of the recommended amount (Fig. 2C; Table-2), suggesting a consistent pattern of fibre inadequacy across the group. In contrast, protein intake frequently exceeded the RNI. The low average sodium, fat and sugar intake possibly reflects health-conscious eating. Although short-term deficits do not confirm clinical deficiency, these results highlight iron, magnesium, potassium and fibre as key targets for nutritional support.

Nutrient	Summary statistics (Mean %RNI \pm SD; p)	Below 100% RNI (n)	At/Above 100% RNI (n)	Total (n)
Vitamin D	39.7 \pm 41.0; p=0.0012	14	0	14
Potassium	68.9 \pm 23.8; p=0.0009	12	2	14
Iron	64.2 \pm 36.6; p=0.0053	11	3	14
Magnesium	79.0 \pm 30.8; p=0.0166	9	5	14
Calcium	88.3 \pm 49.3; p=0.1190	7	7	14
Sodium	63.1 \pm 39.8; p=0.0067	11	3	14
Fibre	44.9 \pm 23.1; p=0.0001	13	1	14
Protein	152 \pm 70.1; p=0.0353	2	12	14

Table-2: Summary statistics of key nutrients deficits during recorded days

Five participants had <50% intake of multiple nutrients over recorded days, all of whom displayed regular meal-skipping behaviour and were privately prescribed (Fig-2A, Table-3). These individuals also reported reduced fruit and vegetable intake (median 5-a-day portions = 1.65 vs. 3.0 in the rest of the cohort), a difference that approached statistical significance (Wilcoxon W = 36, $p = 0.083$, 95% CI: -0.17 to 3.68). Despite some of these participants receiving dietary support (from medication provider) or reporting nutritional competence, they did not appear to achieve fruit- and vegetable-rich diets during the recorded days (Table-3). This suggests that current advice may be insufficiently tailored or inconsistently implemented in practice.

Participant	Avg. 5-a-Day Intake	Nutrition Support/ Knowledge
P04	3.25	Yes
P08	0.50	No
P12	1.65	No
P13	2.75	Yes
P14	3.17	Yes

Table-3: Fruit/veg intake based on average 5-a-day values and nutritional knowledge status in participants with multiple nutrient deficits

Exploratory analyses of UPF intake and fibre adequacy showed no significant association, except that fibre intake increased with total caloric intake; full results are provided in Appendix.7.

4. DISCUSSION

There is a lack of evidence-based nutritional guidance for patients treated with weight-lowering medications¹⁹. Current UK dietary advice is based on The Eatwell Guide 2016,

which is a weight neutral guide, not designed for people with malnutrition in obesity nor those on GLP1-RAs.

Evidence suggests that very low energy diets are usually insufficient to meet micronutrient requirements without significant support or supplementation²⁰. For example, NICE obesity and weight management guidance recommends that low-energy total diet replacement (800-1200kcal/day) should only be considered as part of a multicomponent strategy with long term support with specialist services¹⁴. Notably total diet replacement products are carefully designed to be nutritionally complete in contrast to unsupervised dietary intake by those identified in this study with intakes under 800 calories daily. People undergoing bariatric surgery exhibit increased rates of pre-existing nutritional deficiencies and so are routinely offered nutritional assessments with targeted supplementation¹⁹ in contrast to those using GLP1-RAs who this study shows may also have similarly restricted dietary intake.

This study suggests that myfood24 could facilitate nutritional monitoring and screening for patients using GLP1-RAs. Participants were able to use the platform with minimal support, and three reported that it increased awareness of their own dietary patterns following its use. In this context, myfood24 may have value not only as a research tool but also as part of routine wrap-around care, offering patients an accessible means to learn about their diet and for clinicians to identify nutritional risk. Given time constraints and limited nutrition training in primary care, patient-led use of tools like myfood24 could provide a pragmatic approach to incorporating nutritional screening into standard support.

In summary, this study suggests that there may be critical gaps in the wrap-around care provided to patients who access GLP1-RAs privately or on the NHS. This study also suggests that it is possible that some people using GLP1 RA are consuming under 800 calories which may increase risks of malnutrition²¹. Consistent with recent expert guidance, structured nutritional assessment and ongoing dietary monitoring, alongside access to multidisciplinary support including medical, psychological, and specialist dietary input^{21, 22}, should be considered essential adjuncts in pharmacological weight management. Without these, patients may be at risk of preventable micro and macronutrient deficiencies, muscle loss which are likely to reduce the expected benefits of weight loss.

5. LIMITATIONS

This study was conducted in a large medical practise, in a relatively affluent area of Northants in the UK²⁴. This context likely influenced the findings as access to healthy food and health literacy might be expected to be higher in more socioeconomically advantaged areas. In which case, this study may underestimate the size and impact of the risks of malnutrition with GLP1 RA. This reduces generalisability to the broader population of patients prescribed GLP1-RAs, especially to those living in food-insecure or resource-limited settings, where one might expect more pronounced nutritional deficiency and/or poorer dietary quality. The small sample size, gender imbalance (11 women, 3 men) and high proportion of private prescriptions (71%) may also affect representativeness. Nonetheless, the observation of suboptimal nutrient intakes even within this presumed affluent cohort is striking. Further research is needed to explore these disparities and assess the impact of GLP-1 RAs in more deprived populations.

The use of myfood24 for dietary assessment poses limitations. For participants who completed the tool independently, there was no mechanism to verify the accuracy of their

entries, although the platform provides visual examples of portion sizes and probes for additional information to accurately gather nutrient intake. Some users may have selected ready meals that approximated homemade dishes if they were unaware of the option to input custom recipes. Additionally, the dietary data collected covered only a limited number of days, which may not fully represent typical eating patterns. To reduce this variability, participants were instructed to report days they considered “typical”; however, it is possible that the days measured are not representative of dietary pattern over the longer term.

The use of %UPF as a standalone proxy for nutritional adequacy may be simplistic, as suggested by the lack of association between fibre intake and UPF% from our data. For example, patients with higher overall intake may meet fibre recommendations despite a high %UPF, simply due to greater food volume. This underscores the need to interpret UPF% in context, particularly for nutrients that scale with total intake. Relying solely on UPF% may obscure clinically relevant differences in dietary quality. Alternative composite measures, such as the Healthy Eating Index or Diet Quality Index, could provide a more holistic assessment, while adjusting for total energy intake in modelling may improve interpretability.

The study design also presents certain limitations. For example, the observational design precludes causal inference. Anecdotally, some patients declined participation due to fears their medication might be withdrawn. Also, using self-selection sampling, whereby individuals voluntarily choose to participate, introduces the potential for selection bias. This approach may result in a sample that is not representative of the broader patient population, as individuals who are more motivated, have strong opinions, or possess greater availability are more likely to respond. Additionally, the demographic skew toward participants over the age of 50 limits the generalizability of the findings. As a result, it is challenging to assess how experiences, dietary habits, and the effectiveness of support services may differ among younger patients prescribed GLP1-RAs.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This quality improvement audit underscores the importance of comprehensive nutritional support and adequate emotional and psychological care for patients prescribed GLP1-RAs. While these medications present a promising option for weight management and metabolic health, our findings reveal gaps in the wrap-around services offered to patients. Despite their efficacy in reducing appetite and promoting weight loss, many participants experienced deficiencies in dietary intake on the days reported and largely lacked the necessary support to navigate their nutritional needs effectively. The potential for consumption of very low-calorie diets alongside high reliance on UPFs emphasise the urgent need for structured nutritional assessments, for which myfood24 can be a suitable tool for clinicians, and tailored interventions.

Overall, the findings of this study call for more research into the size and health impacts of unsupervised very low-calorie dietary intake and the impact of these on nutritional status whilst on GLP1-RAs. Future research should systematically investigate dietary patterns among larger and broader populations on GLP1-RAs, particularly in areas marked by socioeconomic disadvantage.

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Footnotes

Contributions: DA and MO contributed equally to data collection and writing the manuscript. DA conducted quantitative dietary analysis and MO conducted qualitative thematic analysis. EF laid the foundation of the study design and supervised DA and MO. The manuscript was critically reviewed by EF, SR and RG.

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